

Apparent Molal Volumes and Thermodynamic Quantities of Viscous Flow for Urea + Ammonium Sulphate Solutions

SATWINDER P. SINGH and O. P. YADAV*

Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar-125 004

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From density measurements, apparent molal volumes (ϕ_v) and volumes of transfer ($\Delta\phi_{v,tr}$) of urea from water to aqueous ammonium sulphate solutions have been obtained. Viscosity data obtained for the system : urea + ammonium sulphate + water, have been used to calculate, using Eyring equation, the thermodynamic quantities (ΔG^* , ΔH^* and ΔS^*) of viscous flow. Measurements have been made at 303.15 and 313.15 K over the urea concentration range 0–5 M and ammonium sulphate concentrations 0.2 and 0.4 M. Ammonium sulphate in aqueous solutions was found to enhance the water-structure. The results have been interpreted in the light of the solute-solvent interactions in aqueous media.

Physicochemical studies of model compounds in their aqueous solutions are of fundamental importance in understanding intermolecular interactions in liquids^{1,2} and the effect of these compounds on water structure³. Tanford⁴ cited evidence suggesting that the relative stability of the structure of viruses, DNA and globular proteins depends upon the molecular structure of water associated with them. Effect of urea on water-structure is not yet clearly understood. While a number of researchers^{5,6} reported that urea in aqueous solutions disrupts the water-structure, Hamdiyyah⁷ interpreted that urea in water is structure-former.

The volumetric and viscosity studies can provide a meaningful information regarding solute-solute and solute-solvent interaction in solutions. The present work reports apparent molal volume (ϕ_v), volume of transfer ($\Delta\phi_{v,tr}$) and the thermodynamic quantities (ΔG^* , ΔH^* and ΔS^*) of viscous flow for the aqueous solutions containing urea and ammonium sulphate. Urea and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ have been chosen because of their usage as fertilizer ingredients and protein denaturants in aqueous solutions. Density and viscosity measurements have been carried out at 303.15 and 313.15 K over the urea concentration range 0–5 M and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ concentrations 0.2 and 0.4 M. The results have been interpreted in the light of solute-solvent intermolecular interactions in aqueous media.

Results and Discussion

Apparent molal volumes (ϕ_v), of urea in water as well as in co-solute solutions were calculated using equation (1),

$$(\phi_v) = \frac{M_2}{d} \left[1 - \frac{1 + (m_3 M_3 / 1000)(d - d_s)}{(m_2 M_2 / 1000)d_s} \right] \quad (1)$$

where, m_2 and m_3 ; M_2 and M_3 are the molalities and molecular weights of urea and the co-solute respectively,

d_s and d represent the densities of the solvent (water in case of urea solutions and 0.2 or 0.4 M co-solute in case of ternary solutions) and the solution respectively. The values of densities and ϕ_v for the studied systems are given in Tables 1–3. The volume of transfer ($\Delta\phi_{v,tr}$), has been calculated using equation,

$$\Delta\phi_{v,tr} = \phi_{v,ter} - \phi_{v,bin} \quad (2)$$

where, $\phi_{v,ter}$ and $\phi_{v,bin}$ represent the apparent molal volumes of urea in ternary (urea + $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ + water) and binary (urea + water) solutions respectively. The values of $\phi_{v,tr}$ for the studied system are also included in Tables 2 and 3.

It is observed that apparent molal volume (ϕ_v) of urea decreases with increase of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ concentration (Fig. 1), suggesting enhancing of liquid structure in the presence of ammonium sulphate. In the absence of ammonium sulphate, ϕ_v values of urea are independent of urea concentration upto 5 M. However, in the presence of ammonium sulphate, as the urea concentration is increased, ϕ_v values

TABLE 1—VALUES OF DENSITY (d) AND APPARENT MOLAL VOLUME (ϕ_v) OF UREA AT ITS DIFFERENT MOLAL CONCENTRATIONS AT 303.15 AND 313.15 K

[Urea], M (mol kg ⁻¹ H ₂ O)	d g cm ⁻³		ϕ_v cm ³ mol ⁻¹	
	303.15 K	313.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
0.00	0.9955	0.9927	60.3	60.3
0.52	1.0034	1.0114	44.5	22.8
1.06	1.0113	1.0077	44.5	45.4
1.63	1.0189	1.0140	44.7	46.1
2.23	1.0265	1.0221	44.8	45.7
2.86	1.0334	1.0298	45.1	45.5
3.52	1.0414	1.0374	44.9	45.6
4.98	1.0561	1.0512	45.1	45.8
6.62	1.0693	1.0664	45.5	45.7

TABLE 2—VALUES OF DENSITY (d), APPARENT MOLAL VOLUME (ϕ_v) AND VOLUME OF TRANSFER ($\phi_{v,tr}$) OF UREA FROM WATER TO AQUEOUS 0.2 M AMMONIUM SULPHATE AT DIFFERENT UREA CONCENTRATIONS

[Urea], m (mol kg ⁻¹ H ₂ O)	d g cm ⁻³		ϕ_v cm ³ mol ⁻¹		$\Delta\phi_{v,tr}$ cm ³ mol ⁻¹	
	303.15 K	313.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
	0.00	0.9963	0.9929	60.3	60.5	-00.1
0.52	1.0182	1.0139	17.4	19.3	-27.1	-03.5
1.06	1.0257	1.0180	31.5	35.9	-13.0	-09.5
1.63	1.0335	1.0284	36.0	37.3	-08.7	-08.8
2.23	1.0411	1.0338	38.3	40.5	-06.4	-05.2
2.86	1.0488	1.0429	39.7	40.9	-05.4	-04.7
3.52	1.0570	1.0503	40.5	41.7	-04.5	-03.8
4.98	1.0693	1.0607	42.4	43.9	-02.7	-01.9
6.62	1.0817	1.0752	43.5	44.4	-02.0	-01.3

TABLE 3—VALUES OF DENSITY (d), APPARENT MOLAL VOLUMES (ϕ_v) AND VOLUMES OF TRANSFER ($\Delta\phi_{v,tr}$) OF UREA FROM WATER TO AQUEOUS 0.4 M AMMONIUM SULPHATE AT DIFFERENT UREA CONCENTRATIONS

[Urea], m (mol kg ⁻¹ H ₂ O)	d g cm ⁻³		ϕ_v cm ³ mol ⁻¹		$\Delta\phi_{v,tr}$ cm ³ mol ⁻¹	
	303.15 K	313.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
	0.00	0.9908	0.9935	60.6	60.5	+00.3
0.52	1.0307	1.0297	-15.8	-08.5	-60.3	-31.3
1.06	1.0388	1.0398	14.7	16.4	-29.9	-29.0
1.63	1.0485	1.0487	23.7	25.4	-21.0	-20.8
2.23	1.0536	1.0558	30.5	30.9	-14.3	-14.8
2.86	1.0584	1.0612	34.6	34.8	-10.5	-10.7
3.52	1.0638	1.0666	37.2	37.2	-07.7	-08.4
4.98	1.0826	1.0835	38.6	38.9	-06.5	-06.9
6.62	1.0945	1.0968	40.7	40.8	-04.8	-04.9

Fig. 1. Plots of apparent molal volume (ϕ_v) of urea as a function of urea concentration and the effect of added $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ at 303.15 K : (O) aqueous urea, (x) urea + water + $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ (0.2 M) and (Δ) urea + water + $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ (0.4 M).

initially increase and then become constant. These results suggest that at low concentration, urea promotes liquid structure but at higher concentrations it disrupts the liquid structure. Earlier, investigators also reported dual role of urea as liquid-structure breaker^{5,6} as well as liquid-structure former⁷. Increase of ϕ_v values with temperature may partly be due to the collapsing of water structure and partly due to the increase of cubical expansion of liquid at higher temperature.

Higher values of $\Delta\phi_{v,tr}$ (Fig. 2) of urea in 0.2 M $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ than in 0.4 M $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ again suggest structure-forming nature of ammonium sulphate. It is believed that the ions of structure-forming salts draw the water molecules towards themselves to form a new compact structure at the expense of the original 'iceberg' structure of water^{8,9}.

The dependence of $\Delta\phi_{v,tr}$ on urea concentration (Fig. 2) again suggests structure-promoting behaviour of urea at lower concentration and structure-breaking at its higher concentrations. Earlier investigators^{10,11} also reported the dual role of urea on its effect on water structure. Whereas

Fig. 2. Plots of volume of transfer ($\Delta\phi_{v,fr}$) of urea from water to aqueous $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ at 303.15 K : (O) urea + water + $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ (0.2 M), (x) urea + water + $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ (0.4 M).

on the basis of dielectric constant measurements for aqueous urea solutions Edsall and Wyman¹⁰ suggested urea to be structure-former, Rupley¹¹ from viscometric studies reported urea as a structure-breaker.

The values of relative viscosities (η_r) at different concentrations of urea are presented in Tables 4–6. According to Jone-Dole's equation¹²,

$$\eta_r = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad (3)$$

where, C is the molar concentration of urea, η_r the relative viscosity of solution, A and B are the parameters representing the measures of solute-solute interaction and solute-solvent interaction respectively, in solution. Since in the present studies, urea concentrations are much higher than 0.1 M, therefore B swamps out the effect of A ¹³. This reduces the Jone-Dole's equation to

$$\eta_r = 1 + BC \quad (4)$$

The values of parameter B (eqn. 4) obtained from the slope of plot between η_r and urea concentration are given in Table 7. B -coefficient values are small and increase with increase in concentration of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, indicating the promotion of liquid structure in the presence of ammonium sulphate. Positive values of B infer liquid-structure forming effect of urea on water. However, small magnitude of B for urea solution suggests weak structure-forming tendency of urea in comparison to electrolytes which have larger Jone-Dole B coefficient values¹⁶.

Free energy of activation of viscous flow (ΔG^*) is another useful parameter to assess the complexity of liquid

TABLE 4—VALUES OF RELATIVE VISCOSITIES (η_r) AND FREE ENERGY OF ACTIVATION OF VISCOUS FLOW (ΔG^*) OF AQUEOUS UREA SOLUTIONS AT DIFFERENT UREA CONCENTRATIONS AT 303.15 K AND 313.15 K

[Urea] mol dm ⁻³	η_r		ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	
	303.15 K	313.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
0.0	0.9999	1.0005	9.06	8.85
0.5	1.0185	1.0237	9.14	8.91
1.0	1.0367	1.0304	9.22	8.99
1.5	1.0601	1.0412	9.30	9.05
2.0	1.0884	1.0595	9.40	9.13
2.5	1.1097	1.1014	9.50	9.22
3.0	1.1461	1.1371	9.61	9.33
4.0	1.2033	1.1578	9.75	9.46
5.0	1.2741	1.2259	9.94	9.65

TABLE 5—VALUES OF RELATIVE VISCOSITY (η_r) AND FREE ENERGY OF ACTIVATION OF VISCOUS FLOW (ΔG^*) OF AQUEOUS UREA SOLUTIONS AT DIFFERENT UREA CONCENTRATIONS IN THE PRESENCE OF 0.2 M $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ AT 303.15 AND 315.15 K

[Urea] mol dm ⁻³	η_r		ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	
	303.15 K	313.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
0.0	0.0006	1.0007	9.12	8.91
0.5	1.0616	1.0254	9.26	8.97
1.0	1.0843	1.0698	9.35	9.12
1.5	1.1211	1.0936	9.46	9.20
2.0	1.1604	1.1212	9.57	9.30
2.5	1.1858	1.1318	9.65	9.34
3.0	1.2132	1.1730	9.73	9.46
4.0	1.2774	1.2383	9.91	9.66
5.0	1.3419	1.3176	10.08	9.86

TABLE 6—VALUES OF RELATIVE VISCOSITIES (η_r) AND FREE ENERGY OF ACTIVATION OF VISCOUS FLOW (ΔG^*) OF AQUEOUS UREA SOLUTIONS AT DIFFERENT UREA CONCENTRATIONS IN THE PRESENCE OF 0.4 M $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ AT 303.15 AND 315.15 K

[Urea] mol dm ⁻³	η_r		ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	
	303.15 K	313.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
0.0	0.9951	1.0012	9.17	8.97
0.5	1.1766	1.0987	9.40	9.16
1.0	1.1620	1.1374	9.54	9.28
1.5	1.1855	1.1664	9.61	9.37
2.0	1.2203	1.1947	9.71	9.46
2.5	1.2684	1.2141	9.84	9.53
3.0	1.3304	1.2463	9.99	9.63
4.0	1.3811	1.3481	10.12	9.87
5.0	1.4938	1.4331	10.33	10.09

TABLE 7—VALUES OF B COEFFICIENT (EQUATION 4) FOR UREA + $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ + WATER SYSTEM AT 303.15 AND 313.15 K

[$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$] mol dm ⁻³	B coefficient	
	303.15 K	313.5 K
0.0	0.050	0.045
0.2	0.064	0.060
0.4	0.088	0.076

structure. Values of ΔG^* were calculated using the Eyring equation¹⁴,

$$1/\eta = (V/hN) \exp(-\Delta G^*/RT) \quad (5)$$

where, h is the Planck constant, N the Avogadro number, V the molar volume of liquid, R the gas constant ($\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$), T the absolute temperature and η the viscosity (poise). ΔG^* values increase with increase of urea concentration (Tables 4–6), suggesting the formation of urea-water complex which controls the fluid motion in these solutions¹³. A further increase in ΔG^* values with the addition of ammonium sulphate again indicates enhancing of liquid structure by $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$. From the values of ΔG^* at 303.15 and 313.15 K entropies (ΔS^*) and enthalpies (ΔH^*) of activation of viscous flow were calculated using equations (6) and (7) respectively,

$$\Delta S_{308.15}^* = -(\Delta G_{313.15}^* - \Delta G_{303.15}^*)/10 \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta H^* = \Delta G^* + T\Delta S^* \quad (7)$$

The values of ΔG^* for the studied systems are given in Tables 4–6 and ΔH^* and ΔS^* values are given in Table 8. Entropy and enthalpy of activation of viscous flow thus calculated at 308.15 increase (in urea + H_2O) regularly over

TABLE 8—VALUES OF ENTROPY (ΔS^* , $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$) AND ENTHALPY (ΔH^* , kJ mol^{-1}) OF ACTIVATION FOR VISCOUS FLOW AT 308.15 K

[Urea] mol dm ⁻³	Urea+ H_2O		Urea+ H_2O +0.2M $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$		Urea+ H_2O +0.4M $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	
	ΔS^*	ΔH^*	ΔS^*	ΔH^*	ΔS^*	ΔH^*
0.0	21	15.4	21	15.5	20	15.2
0.5	23	16.1	23	16.2	24	16.8
1.0	23	16.2	24	16.6	26	17.4
1.5	25	16.9	26	17.3	24	16.9
2.0	27	17.6	27	17.8	25	17.3
2.5	28	18.0	31	19.1	31	19.2
3.0	28	18.1	27	17.9	36	20.9
4.0	29	18.6	26	17.8	25	17.7
5.0	29	18.7	22	16.8	24	17.6

the entire concentration range studied for urea. However, for ternary solutions (urea + H_2O + ammonium sulphate), ΔS^* and ΔH^* first increase till 3 M urea and then showing a decrease in these quantities at still higher concentrations of urea. These results again suggest enhancing of water structure at lower concentration of urea and a disruption of liquid structure at its higher concentrations.

Experimental

Urea (E. Merck) and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ (Sarabhai Merck) were used as supplied. Double-distilled water was used for the preparation of the solutions.

Density was determined using a bicapillary pyknometer¹⁵ with an accuracy of $\pm 5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$. Relative viscosity was obtained using a modified Ostwald type viscometer. Kinetic energy correction for viscosity data was not needed since the time of flow for each solution exceeded 280 (± 0.1) s. Temperature of water thermostat was maintained within ± 0.01 K.

References

1. N. SWAIN and V. CHAKRAVORTY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1996, **35**, 395.
2. T. M. AMINABHAVI and S. S. JOSHI, *Indian J. Technol.*, 1992, **30**, 197.
3. W. P. JENCKS, "Catalysis in Chemistry and Enzymology", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1969.
4. C. TANFORD, "Enzyme Models and Enzyme Structure", Office of Technical Services, U.S. Dept. of Commerce, Washington, D. C., 1962.
5. H. S. FRANK and W. Y. WEN, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, **24**, 133.
6. W. A. HARGRAVES and G. C. KRESHECK, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, **73**, 3249.
7. A. M. HAMIDIYYAH, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 2720.
8. H. S. FRANK in "The Proceedings of the Conference on Desalination Research", Publication 942 of National Academy of Sciences, National Research Council, Washington, D. C., 1963, p. 141.
9. I. G. MIKHANILOV and YU. P. SYRNIKOV, *Zh. Strukt. Khim.*, 1960, **12**, 1.
10. J. T. EDSALL and J. WYMAN, "Biophysical Chemistry", Academic, New York, 1958.
11. J. A. RUPLEY, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **68**, 2002.
12. G. JONES and D. J. DOLE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 2959.
13. S. MOHANTY and P. B. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 1059.
14. S. GLASSTONE, K. J. LAIDER and H. EYRING, "Theory of Rate Processes", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1941.
15. D. V. S. JAIN, B. S. LARK, S. S. CHAMAK and P. CHANDER, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 845.
16. R. W. GURNEY, "Ionic Processes in Solution", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1953.